

CODECHECK certificate 2020-025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279275>

Item	Value
Title	The application of Local Indicators for Categorical Data (LICD) to explore spatial dependence in archaeological spaces
Authors	Francesco Carrer
Reference	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2020.105306
Codechecker	Daniel Nüst
Date of check	2020-11-19 12:00:00
Summary	This workflow was very straightforward to check following the authors' README. All figures stored in the repository could be recreated and match the ones given in the manuscript.
Repository	https://github.com/codecheckers/LICD_article

Table 1: CODECHECK summary

Output	Comment	Size (b)
<code>Torridge_HLC.jpeg</code>	Figure 3	498208
<code>Torridge_LICD.jpeg</code>	Figure 4	176077
<code>jc_out.csv</code>	data for Table 2	2168
<code>HLC_output.Rout</code>	Verbatim console output of LICD-Archaeo-HCL.R captured by sink, including messages	12334
<code>barmose_jc_out.csv</code>	data for Table 3	738
<code>Barmose_Grid_Cores.jpeg</code>	Figure 5	154525
<code>Barmose_LICD_class.jpeg</code>	Figure 6	144274
<code>Grid_output.Rout</code>	Verbatim console output of LICD-Archaeo-Grid.R captured by sink, including messages	12226

Table 2: Summary of output files generated

Summary

This workflow was very straightforward to check following the authors' README. All figures stored in the repository could be recreated and match the ones given in the manuscript.

CODECHECKER notes

I forked the [GitHub repo provided by the authors](#) into the codecheckers organisation: [codecheckers/LICD_article](#). This evaluation is based on the commit [2665bb2761eb00d8fd929d390682c76e628c4f8b](#). The authors deposited the contents of the repository on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4283766>.

The repository contains some R code and a number of `.jpeg` files. Data is downloaded as part of the scripts.

I went through the steps in the README, and only had to install a few packages that were not available on my system yet. Using the provided `DESCRIPTION` file, I installed dependencies with `devtools::install_deps()`. Thanks to the solid documentation within the scripts and the readable code, I also knew to use the development version of the package `mapview`.

This took around 25 minutes to complete on my laptop (8 cores, 40 GB RAM, SSD). From the diff between the captures outputs, it's quite easy to see the differences in the computing environments, but that no relevant problems occurred during execution. I briefly confirmed the workflow also runs in an `rocker/geospatial:4.0.3` container.

Recommendations to authors

The code was well documented and worked flawlessly on my local machine, there are a few things the authors could consider for their next workflow publication, some of which the authors already picked up in a revision of their repository.

- (authors added `DESCRIPTION` file) use `renv` package or a `DESCRIPTION` file to define the dependencies (= use R package structure)
- (authors updated README) document in README that development version of package `mapview` is needed
- (authors updated README) the interactive map is a bonus compared to the paper - mention how to get to it in the README (the `.zip` file)
- (authors created Zenodo record) deposit a copy of your repo on Zenodo to make the workflow citable and archived
- The data could possibly be republished with the workflow just to be sure, since it is available under open licenses; I can't judge the long term availability of the used download URLs

Manifest files

Torridge_HLC.jpeg

Comment: Figure 3

Torridge_LICD.jpeg

Comment: Figure 4

jc_out.csv

Summary statistics of tabular data:

```
-- Data Summary -----
Name                Values
Number of rows      read.csv(path)
                    18
Number of columns    7

-----
Column type frequency:
character            2
numeric              5

-----
Group variables      None

-- Variable type: character -----
skim_variable n_missing complete_rate  min  max empty
1 order        0             1      5    6    0
2 JCS          0             1     13   27    0
n_unique whitespace
1      3         0
2      6         0

-- Variable type: numeric -----
skim_variable n_missing complete_rate  mean  sd
1 Joincount    0             1 524.  353.
2 Expected     0             1 524.  374.
3 Variance     0             1  34.6  37.0
4 z.value      0             1   1.22  6.04
5 pvalue       0             1   0.416 0.443
  p0      p25      p50      p75      p100 hist
1 5.48e+ 1 309.    422.    811.    1138.
2 5.32e+ 1 289.    407.    839.    1147.
3 1.57e+ 0 10.3     18.9    46.8    139.
4 -8.68e+ 0 -3.07     0.665   5.24    11.3
5 4.08e-30 0.0000241 0.254   0.995   1
```

HLC_output.Rout

```
> sink(zz, type = "message")

> # Loading libraries
> library(sf)

> library(spdep)

> library(tmap)

> library(units)

> library(Matrix)

> # Importing Devon HLC shapefile
> zipfile <- "https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/catalogue/adpdata/arch-2090-1/dissemination/zip/rawhlc.zip"

> ## subject to https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/termsOfUseAndAccess.xhtml
> ## It can be cited by https://doi.org/10.5284/1032952
>
> td .... [TRUNCATED]

> download.file(zipfile, destfile=file.path(td, "rawhlc.zip"))
trying URL 'https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/catalogue/adpdata/arch-2090-1/dissemination/zip/rawhlc.zip'
Content type 'application/zip' length 23188797 bytes (22.1 MB)
=====
downloaded 22.1 MB

> fls <- unzip(file.path(td, "rawhlc.zip"), exdir=td, overwrite=TRUE)

> devon_hlc <- st_read(file.path(td, "rawhlc.shp"), crs=27700)
Reading layer `rawhlc' from data source `/tmp/RtmpDaLJtN/rawhlc.shp' using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
Simple feature collection with 49485 features and 36 fields
geometry type: MULTIPOLYGON
dimension: XY
bbox: xmin: 220832 ymin: 34922.78 xmax: 337602.9 ymax: 148712.1
projected CRS: OSGB 1936 / British National Grid

> ## clip to Torridge District boundary
>
> torridge_bys <- "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/digital-land/boundary-collection/master/collection/loc ..." ... [TRUNCATED]

> ## subject to https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/
> bdy <- st_read(torridge_bys)
Reading layer `index' from data source `https://raw.githubusercontent.com/digital-land/boundary-collection/master/collection/local-authority/E0700...'
Simple feature collection with 1 feature and 10 fields
geometry type: MULTIPOLYGON
dimension: XY
bbox: xmin: -4.680689 ymin: 50.64654 xmax: -3.883846 ymax: 51.20254
geographic CRS: WGS 84

> ## initially created with sf linked to GEOS 3.9.0dev, with OverlayNG
> ## without OverlayNG, intersection fails because of topology errors
> ## req .... [TRUNCATED]

> ## Create ordered factor
>
>
> hlc$class <- ifelse(hlc$PERIOD1 %in% c("Modern", "Post-medieval"), hlc$PERIOD1, "Medieval")

> hlc$class <- ordered(hlc$class, levels=c("Modern", "Post-medieval", "Medieval"))

> ## Map classes
>
> HLC_map <- tm_shape(hlc) +
+ tm_fill("class", palette="viridis", title="Character\nTypes") +
+ tm_compass(position=c("left ..." ... [TRUNCATED])

> # tiff("Torridge_HLC.tiff", width=15, height=15, units="cm", res=300)
> # HLC_map
> # dev.off()
> jpeg("Torridge_HLC.jpeg", width=15, height=15, uni .... [TRUNCATED]

> HLC_map

> dev.off()
null device
1
```

```

> ## Create neighbours
> nb1 <- poly2nb(hlc, snap=4, row.names=as.character(hlc$ID))

> hlc.nb <- nblag(nb1, 3) ## higher orders

> hlc.mat <- as(nb2listw(nblag_cumul(hlc.nb), style="B"), "CsparseMatrix")

> ## Join-Count Statistics
>
> jc.hlc <- vector(mode="list", length=length(hlc.nb))

> jc.hlc.p <- vector(mode="list", length=length(hlc.nb))

> for (i in 1:length(hlc.nb)) {
+   jc.hlc[[i]] <- joincount.multi(hlc$class, nb2listw(hlc.nb[[i]]))
+   jc.hlc.p[[i]] <- pnorm(jc.hlc[[i]][,4], lower .... [TRUNCATED])

> ## Exporting output
>
> jcs <- do.call("rbind", jc.hlc)[-c(7, 14, 21),]

> jcps <- do.call("c", jc.hlc.p)[-c(7, 14, 21)]

> (jc_out <- data.frame(order=rep(c("First", "Second", "Third"), each=6), JCS=row.names(jcs), as.data.frame(cbind(jcs, pvalue=jcps)), row.names=NULL)
  order      JCS  Joincount  Expected  Variance   z.value      pvalue
1 First      Modern:Modern  771.12427  839.00207  102.175599 -6.71512609 1.000000e+00
2 First Post-medieval:Post-medieval 345.60261  391.89976  59.981162 -5.97787566 1.000000e+00
3 First      Medieval:Medieval  54.80680  53.16675  9.973976  0.51930739 3.017732e-01
4 First      Post-medieval:Modern 1091.05970 1147.26492 139.398052 -4.76045268 9.999990e-01
5 First      Medieval:Modern  514.64644  422.73095  65.680018 11.34154148 4.084633e-30
6 First      Medieval:Post-medieval 365.76018  288.93556  48.634518 11.01610665 1.597925e-28
7 Second     Modern:Modern  839.46923  839.00207  30.997060  0.08390832 4.665647e-01
8 Second Post-medieval:Post-medieval 418.01951  391.89976  18.034020  6.15067428 3.857711e-10
9 Second     Medieval:Medieval  71.31331  53.16675  2.955733 10.55508654 2.405980e-26
10 Second    Post-medieval:Modern 1091.47783 1147.26492 41.291714 -8.68164898 1.000000e+00
11 Second    Medieval:Modern  425.29930  422.73095  19.659496  0.57925259 2.812094e-01
12 Second    Medieval:Post-medieval 297.42082  288.93556  14.480309  2.22985407 1.287857e-02
13 Third     Modern:Modern  824.51919  839.00207  18.046848 -3.40921464 9.996742e-01
14 Third Post-medieval:Post-medieval 394.30714  391.89976  10.147943  0.75571103 2.249112e-01
15 Third     Medieval:Medieval  60.36025  53.16675  1.569199  5.74250544 4.664294e-09
16 Third     Post-medieval:Modern 1137.75125 1147.26492 21.881608 -2.03379977 9.790141e-01
17 Third     Medieval:Modern  435.02278  422.73095  10.870555  3.72812692 9.645411e-05
18 Third     Medieval:Post-medieval 291.03939  288.93556  7.837674  0.75148029 2.261818e-01

> write.csv(jc_out, "jc_out.csv", row.names=FALSE)

> #####
> ## Boots' LICD (from Bivand et al. 2017) ##
> #####
> # For h .... [TRUNCATED]
>           [,1]
Modern      0.5167038
Post-medieval 0.3531658
Medieval    0.1301304

> areas <- aggregate(st_area(hlc), list(hlc$class), sum)

> areas$x <- set_units(areas$x, "km2")

> areas$props <- drop_units(areas$x/sum(areas$x))

> areas
  Group.1      x      props
1 Modern 451.1156 [km^2] 0.4593523
2 Post-medieval 271.3623 [km^2] 0.2763170
3 Medieval 259.5909 [km^2] 0.2643307

> adata <- as.numeric(hlc$class) #factor no longer necessary, now numeric

> source("local_JC0.R")

> res <- local_JC0(obj=hlc, lagsmat=hlc.mat, varname="class", numvar=adata, p=p)

> local_comp <- res[[1]]

> JC.pvalue_seq <- res[[2]]

> ##### STEP 2: local configuration
>

```

```

> local_config <- matrix(0,length(adata),1)

> colnames(local_config) <- c("cluster-dispersion")

> for (j in 1:length(adata)){#for cluster is 1, for dispersion -1, otherwise 0
+   if (min(JC.pvalue_seq[j,])<1-(1-0.05)^(1/3)){ ###CHANGE
+     ifels .... [TRUNCATED]

> # Combination of local composition and local configuration
> Type <- character(length=length(adata))

> C <- cbind(local_comp, local_config)

> for (i in 1:length(adata)){
+   ifelse(C[i,1] == 1 && C[i,2] == 1, Type[i] <- "Cluster",
+         ifelse(C[i,1] == 1 && C[i,2] == 0, Type[i] <- "C ..." ... [TRUNCATED]

> # Plot LICD - TIFF + JPEG
> Type1 <- Type

> hlc$Type <- Type

> is.na(Type1) <- Type1 == "No cluster"

> hlc$Type1 <- factor(Type1)

> LICD_map <- tm_shape(hlc) +
+   tm_fill("Type1", palette="viridis", title="LICD", textNA="No cluster") +
+   tm_compass(position=c("left", "bottom ..." ... [TRUNCATED]

> # tiff("Torridge_LICD.tiff", width=15, height=15, units="cm", res=300)
> # LICD_map
> # dev.off()
> jpeg("Torridge_LICD.jpeg", width=15, height=15, .... [TRUNCATED]

> LICD_map

> dev.off()
null device
1

> # HLC & LICD
>
> both <- LICD_map + tm_facets("class", nrow=2)

> jpeg("Torridge_HLC_LICD.jpeg",width=30,height=25,units="cm",res=300)

> both

> dev.off()
null device
1

> # mapview installed from "r-spatial/mapview" after #336 #327 #323
> library(mapview)

> packageVersion("mapview")
[1] '2.9.4'

> if (unname(sf_extSoftVersion()["GDAL"]) >= "3.1.0") mapviewOptions(fgb = FALSE)

> file.remove("HLC_map.html")
[1] FALSE

> file.remove("HLC_map.zip")
[1] TRUE

> cl <- mapview(hlc, zcol="class")

> ty <- mapview(hlc, zcol="Type")

> mapshot(cl + ty, url = paste0(getwd(), "/HLC_map.html"))

> zip("HLC_map.zip", "HLC_map.html")

> file.remove("HLC_map.html")
[1] TRUE

> sessionInfo()
R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)

```

Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
Running under: Ubuntu 20.04 LTS

Matrix products: default

BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/libblas.so.3

LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/liblapack.so.3

locale:

[1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8	LC_NUMERIC=C	LC_TIME=de_DE.UTF-8	LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8
[5] LC_MONETARY=de_DE.UTF-8	LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8	LC_PAPER=de_DE.UTF-8	LC_NAME=C
[9] LC_ADDRESS=C	LC_TELEPHONE=C	LC_MEASUREMENT=de_DE.UTF-8	LC_IDENTIFICATION=C

attached base packages:

[1] stats graphics grDevices utils datasets methods base

other attached packages:

[1] stars_0.4-3	abind_1.4-5	spatstat_1.64-1	rpart_4.1-15	nlme_3.1-150	spatstat.data_1.5-2
[7] archdata_1.2	mapview_2.9.4	Matrix_1.2-18	units_0.6-7	tmap_3.2	spdep_1.1-5
[13] spData_0.3.8	sp_1.4-4	sf_0.9-6			

loaded via a namespace (and not attached):

[1] colorspace_2.0-0	leafem_0.1.3	deldir_0.2-3	ellipsis_0.3.1	class_7.3-17
[6] leaflet_2.0.3	rprojroot_2.0.2	dadjoke_0.1.2	cranlike_1.0.2	satellite_1.0.2
[11] base64enc_0.1-3	fs_1.5.0	dichromat_2.0-0	rstudioapi_0.13	farver_2.0.3
[16] remotes_2.2.0	bit64_4.0.5	fansi_0.4.1	codetools_0.2-18	splines_4.0.3
[21] knitr_1.30	polyclip_1.10-0	pkgload_1.1.0	jsonlite_1.7.1	tmaptools_3.1
[26] png_0.1-7	compiler_4.0.3	httr_1.4.2	assertthat_0.2.1	cli_2.2.0
[31] leaflet.providers_1.9.0	htmltools_0.5.0	prettyunits_1.1.1	tools_4.0.3	coda_0.19-4
[36] glue_1.4.2	dplyr_1.0.2	rappdirs_0.3.1	gmodels_2.18.1	Rcpp_1.0.5
[41] raster_3.4-5	vctrs_0.3.5	svglite_1.2.3.2	gdata_2.18.0	debugme_1.1.0
[46] leafsync_0.1.0	crosstalk_1.1.0.1	lwgeom_0.2-5	xfun_0.19	stringr_1.4.0
[51] ps_1.4.0	testthat_3.0.0	parsedate_1.2.0	lifecycle_0.2.0	gttools_3.8.2
[56] devtools_2.3.2	goftest_1.2-2	XML_3.99-0.5	LearnBayes_2.15.1	MASS_7.3-53
[61] scales_1.1.1	spatstat.utils_1.17-0	clisymbols_1.2.0	parallel_4.0.3	expm_0.999-5
[66] rematch2_2.1.2	RColorBrewer_1.1-2	yaml_2.2.1	curl_4.3	memoise_1.1.0
[71] gdtools_0.2.2	stringi_1.5.3	RSQLite_2.2.1	desc_1.2.0	leafpop_0.0.6
[76] e1071_1.7-4	crancache_0.0.0.9001	boot_1.3-25	pkgbuild_1.1.0	repr_1.1.0
[81] systemfonts_0.3.2	rlang_0.4.8	pkgconfig_2.0.3	prompt_1.0.0	evaluate_0.14
[86] lattice_0.20-41	tensor_1.5	purrr_0.3.4	htmlwidgets_1.5.2	bit_4.0.4
[91] processx_3.4.4	tidyselect_1.1.0	magrittr_2.0.1	R6_2.5.0	generics_0.1.0
[96] DBI_1.1.0	mgcv_1.8-33	pillar_1.4.7	withr_2.3.0	tibble_3.0.4
[101] crayon_1.3.4	uuid_0.1-4	KernSmooth_2.23-18	rmarkdown_2.5	usethis_1.6.3
[106] grid_4.0.3	blob_1.2.1	callr_3.5.1	git2r_0.27.1	webshot_0.5.2
[111] digest_0.6.27	classInt_0.4-3	brew_1.0-6	stats4_4.0.3	munsell_0.5.0
[116] viridisLite_0.3.0	skimr_2.1.2	sessioninfo_1.1.1		

> sf_extSoftVersion()

GEOS	GDAL	proj.4	GDAL_with_GEOS	USE_PROJ_H
"3.8.1"	"3.1.3"	"7.1.1"	"true"	"true"

> sink(type = "message")

> sink()

barmose_jc_out.csv

Summary statistics of tabular data:

```
-- Data Summary -----
Name                Values
Number of rows     read.csv(path)
Number of columns   6
                   7
-----
Column type frequency:
character           2
numeric            5
-----
Group variables     None

-- Variable type: character -----
skim_variable n_missing complete_rate  min  max empty
1 order                0           1    5    6    0
2 JCS                  0           1    9   15    0
n_unique whitespace
1      2              0
2      3              0

-- Variable type: numeric -----
skim_variable n_missing complete_rate  mean  sd
1 Joincount      0           1 17.8  7.49
2 Expected       0           1 17.8  8.75
3 Variance       0           1 0.804 0.568
4 z.value        0           1 0.583 2.42
5 pvalue         0           1 0.404 0.451
  p0    p25   p50   p75   p100 hist
1 7.72  11.8  21.3  23.3  24.0
2 6.63  10.5  22.1  24.1  24.7
3 0.335 0.489 0.533 0.977 1.83
4 -3.10 -0.727 0.848 2.37 3.28
5 0.000522 0.0117 0.302 0.757 0.999
```

Barmose_Grid_Cores.jpeg

Comment: Figure 5

Barmose_LICD_class.jpeg

Comment: Figure 6

Grid_output.Rout

```
> sink(zz, type = "message")
> # Import data from CRAN
> library(archdata)
> data("BarmoseI.grid")
> data("BarmoseI.pp")
> Easts <- sort(unique(BarmoseI.grid$East))
> Norths <- sort(unique(BarmoseI.grid$North))
> BarmoseI_Cores.pp <- BarmoseI.pp[BarmoseI.pp[, "Label"]=="Cores",]
> library(spatstat)
> BarmoseI_Cores.ppp <- ppp(BarmoseI_Cores.pp$East, BarmoseI_Cores.pp$North, window=owin(xrange=c(0, max(Easts)+1), yrange=c(0, max(Norths)+1)))
> summary(BarmoseI_Cores.ppp)
Planar point pattern: 81 points
Average intensity 0.4821429 points per square unit
Coordinates are given to 2 decimal places
i.e. rounded to the nearest multiple of 0.01 units
Window: rectangle = [0, 12] x [0, 14] units
Window area = 168 square units
> # Convert to stars array
> library(stars)
> packageVersion("stars")
[1] '0.4.3'
> BarmoseI.grid1 <- BarmoseI.grid
> if (packageVersion("stars") < "0.4.4") {
+   BarmoseI.grid1$North <- BarmoseI.grid1$North + 1
+ } else {
+   BarmoseI.grid1$North <- BarmoseI.grid1$ ... [TRUNCATED]
> # data registered to SW cell corner, stars bug 0.4-2, 0.4-3 and 0.4-4 before
> # late October 2020; stars >= 0.4-2 required by current tmap;
> # stars ... [TRUNCATED]
> # impose a plate carree projection to satisfy tmap
> st_crs(rast) <- 32662
> rast1 <- rast
> rast1$logp1_Debitage <- log10(rast1$Debitage+1)
> # convert to sf data.frame
> library(sf)
> barmose0 <- st_as_sf(rast)
> barmose <- barmose0[!is.na(barmose0$Debitage),]
> cores <- st_as_sf(BarmoseI_Cores.pp, coords=c("East", "North"))
> # impose a plate carree projection to satisfy tmap
> st_crs(cores) <- 32662
> jpeg("Barmose_Grid_Check.jpeg", width=15, height=17, units="cm", res=300)
> opar <- par(no.readonly=TRUE)
> par(mar=c(0,0,0,0)+0.1)
> plot(BarmoseI_Cores.ppp, chars=24, pt.bg="grey", cex=0.7, legend=FALSE)
> abline(v=Easts, lwd=0.5, lty=2)
> abline(h=Norths, lwd=0.5, lty=2)
> points(North ~ East, BarmoseI.grid, pch=3)
```

```

> plot(st_geometry(barmose), add=TRUE, lwd=0.5, border="orange")

> par(opar)

> dev.off()
null device
  1

> library(tmap)

> Log_Deb_map <- tm_shape(rast1, unit="m") +
+   tm_raster("logp1_Debitage", n=7, palette="viridis",
+   title="Debitage\n(log count)") +
+   ... [TRUNCATED]

> jpeg("Barmose_Grid_Cores.jpeg", width=15, height=17, units="cm", res=300)

> Log_Deb_map

> dev.off()
null device
  1

> barmose$cores <- sapply(st_intersects(barmose, cores), length)

> barmose$class <- factor((barmose$cores>0)+0, levels=c(0, 1), labels=c("No Core", "Core"))

> sum(barmose$cores) # 86 for stars 0.4-4 and using sf::st_intersects
[1] 84

> table(barmose$cores)

 0  1  2  3  4  5  6  7
69 19  8  2  5  2  1  1

> # 0  1  2  3  4  5  6  9
> # 69 18 11  2  2  1  3  1
> table(barmose$class)

No Core   Core
     69     38

> # NC C
> # 69 38
>
> class_map <- tm_shape(barmose, unit="m") +
+   tm_fill("class", palette="viridis") +
+   tm_shape(cores, unit="m") +
+   ... [TRUNCATED]

> jpeg("Barmose_class_Cores.jpeg", width=15, height=17, units="cm", res=300)

> class_map

> dev.off()
null device
  1

> # Create neighbours
>
> ## Contiguity neighbours 1-order, 1 = 3 - USE ONLY WHEN WINDOW IS LARGER THAN 1ST ORDER!
>
> library(spdep)

> nb1 <- poly2nb(barmose)

> barmose.nb <- nblag(nb1, 2) ## higher orders

> barmose.mat <- as(nb2listw(nblag_cumul(barmose.nb), style="B"), "CsparseMatrix")

> # Join-Count Statistics
> ## JC for contiguity
>
> jc.barmose <- vector(mode="list", length=length(barmose.nb))

> jc.barmose.p <- vector(mode="list", length=length(barmose.nb))

> for (i in 1:length(barmose.nb)) {
+   jc.barmose[[i]] <- jointcount.multi(barmose$class, nb2listw(barmose.nb[[i]]))
+   jc.barmose.p[[i]] <- pnorm(jc ... [TRUNCATED]

```

```

> ## Exporting output
>
> jcs <- do.call("rbind", jc.barmose)[-c(4, 8),]
> jcps <- do.call("c", jc.barmose.p)[-c(4, 8)]
> (jc_out <- data.frame(order=rep(c("First", "Second"), each=3), JCS=rownames(jcs), as.data.frame(cbind(jcs, pvalue=jcps)), row.names=NULL))
  order      JCS Joincount Expected Variance    z.value    pvalue
1 First No Core:No Core 24.044048 22.132075 0.5678672  2.5372203 0.0055868304
2 First   Core:Core  8.915476  6.632075 0.4851153  3.2783827 0.0005220186
3 First   Core:No Core 20.540476 24.735849 1.8256763 -3.1049791 0.9990485376
4 Second No Core:No Core 22.001997 22.132075 0.4986978 -0.1841983 0.5730710605
5 Second   Core:Core  7.720851  6.632075 0.3352042  1.8805452 0.0300169049
6 Second   Core:No Core 23.777151 24.735849 1.1140353 -0.9083061 0.8181417412

> write.csv(jc_out, "barmose_jc_out.csv", row.names=FALSE)

> #####
> ## Boots' LICD (from Boots 2003) ##
> #####
> ## Set column with ... [TRUNCATED]

> adata <- factor(barmose[[c1m]]) #object with "levels" (factor)

> #### STEP 1: local composition
> p <- (as.matrix(summary(adata)))/length(adata) #probabilities of each "type"

> adata <- as.numeric(adata) #factor no longer necessary, now numeric

> ## Routine 1 ##
> # cluster has 5 columns: 1 - number of units of the "type" as the unit j in the "window
> # 2 - probability of the "type", 3 ..." ... [TRUNCATED]

> c1 <- c2 <- c3 <- c4 <- c5 <- numeric(length(adata))

> for (i in 1:length(adata)) {
+   c1[i] <- (barmose.mat[i,] %*% ifelse(adata==2,1,0))+ifelse(adata[i]==2,1,0)
+   c2[i] <- p[2]
+   c3[i] <- su ... [TRUNCATED]

> cluster <- cbind(c1, c2, c3, c4, c5)

> cluster[is.nan(cluster)]<- 1

> ## End of routine 1 ##
>
> ### Custer-outlier analysis -> result of local composition ###
> sc <- 1-(1-0.05)^(1/2) #Sidak correction, 0.05 ... [TRUNCATED]

> local_comp <- ifelse(cluster[,4]< sc, 1, ifelse(cluster[,5]< sc, 0, -1))

> # 1 for black, 0 for white, -1 - black-white
>
> ##### STEP 2: local configuration
>
> ## Routine 2 ##
> ## We built empirical distrib ... [TRUNCATED]

> for (j in 1:length(adata)) {
+   barmose.mat.1 <- barmose.mat[j,] #extracting a row from weights matrix
+   ktore <- which(barmose.mat.1!=0, ar ... [TRUNCATED]

> ## End of routine 2 ##
>
> colnames(JC.pvalue_seq) <- c("1:1X>=x", "0:0X>=x", "1:0X>=x")

> local_config <- matrix(3,length(adata),1)

> scJC <- 1-(1-0.05)^(1/3) # Sidak correction JC - 3 tests!

> #scJC <- 0.05 #standard
>
> ### Routine 3 Local configuration
>
> local_config <- matrix(nrow=length(adata), ncol=1)

> for (j in 1:length(adata)) {#for black is 1, for white is 0, for black-white is -1, otherwise -2
+   if (min(JC.pvalue_seq[j,])<scJC){
+     ife ... [TRUNCATED]

```

```

> ## End of routine 3 ##
> colnames(local_config) <- c("cluster-dispersion")

> # Combination of local composition and local configuration
> Type <- character(length(adata))

> C <- cbind(local_comp, local_config)

> for (i in 1:length(adata)){
+   ifelse(C[i,1] == 1 && C[i,2] == 1, Type[i] <- "Hot Clump",
+         ifelse(C[i,1] == 1 && (C[i,2] == -2 || C[i,2] .... [TRUNCATED])

> barmose$Type <- factor(Type)

> types_map <- tm_shape(barmose, unit="m") +
+   tm_fill("Type", palette="viridis") +
+   tm_scale_bar(breaks=c(0,1,2), position=c("right", "bottom" ... [TRUNCATED])

> jpeg("Barmose_types_Cores.jpeg", width=15, height=17, units="cm", res=300)

> types_map

> dev.off()
null device
  1

> # Plot Cores + LICD - TIFF + JPEG
>
> LICDClass <- interaction(barmose$class, barmose$Type, sep=" ")

> barmose$LICDClass <- factor(LICDClass, levels=c("Core Hot only", "Core Clump only (Hot)", "Core Hot Clump", "Core No cluster", "No Core Hot only

> LICDClass_map <- tm_shape(barmose, unit="m") +
+   tm_fill("LICDClass", palette="--viridis", title="Classes + LICD") +
+   tm_scale_bar(breaks=c(0, ... [TRUNCATED])

> jpeg("Barmose_LICD_class.jpeg", width=15, height=17, units="cm", res=300)

> LICDClass_map

> dev.off()
null device
  1

> sessionInfo()
R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)
Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
Running under: Ubuntu 20.04 LTS

Matrix products: default
BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/libblas.so.3
LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/liblapack.so.3

locale:
 [1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8      LC_NUMERIC=C              LC_TIME=de_DE.UTF-8      LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8
 [5] LC_MONETARY=de_DE.UTF-8  LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8 LC_PAPER=de_DE.UTF-8    LC_NAME=C
 [9] LC_ADDRESS=C            LC_TELEPHONE=C          LC_MEASUREMENT=de_DE.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C

attached base packages:
[1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods   base

other attached packages:
[1] stars_0.4-3      abind_1.4-5      spatstat_1.64-1  rpart_4.1-15     nlme_3.1-150     spatstat.data_1.5-2
[7] archdata_1.2    mapview_2.9.4    Matrix_1.2-18    units_0.6-7      tmap_3.2         spdep_1.1-5
[13] spData_0.3.8    sp_1.4-4         sf_0.9-6

loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
 [1] colorspace_2.0-0      leafem_0.1.3      deldir_0.2-3      ellipsis_0.3.1    class_7.3-17
 [6] leaflet_2.0.3         rprojroot_2.0.2  dadjoke_0.1.2     cranlike_1.0.2    satelllite_1.0.2
[11] base64enc_0.1-3      fs_1.5.0          dichromat_2.0-0  rstudioapi_0.13   farver_2.0.3
[16] remotes_2.2.0        bit64_4.0.5      fansi_0.4.1       codetools_0.2-18 splines_4.0.3
[21] knitr_1.30           polyclip_1.10-0  pkgload_1.1.0    jsonlite_1.7.1    tmaptools_3.1
[26] png_0.1-7            compiler_4.0.3    httr_1.4.2        assertthat_0.2.1 cli_2.2.0
[31] leaflet.providers_1.9.0 htmltools_0.5.0  prettyunits_1.1.1 tools_4.0.3       coda_0.19-4
[36] glue_1.4.2           dplyr_1.0.2      rappdirs_0.3.1   gmodels_2.18.1    Rcpp_1.0.5
[41] raster_3.4-5         vctr_0.3.5       svglite_1.2.3.2  gdata_2.18.0     debugme_1.1.0
[46] leafsync_0.1.0       crosstalk_1.1.0.1 lwgeom_0.2-5     xfun_0.19         stringr_1.4.0
[51] ps_1.4.0            testthat_3.0.0   parsedate_1.2.0  lifecycle_0.2.0  gtools_3.8.2
[56] devtools_2.3.2      goftest_1.2-2    XML_3.99-0.5     LearnBayes_2.15.1 MASS_7.3-53
[61] scales_1.1.1         spatstat.utils_1.17-0 clisymbols_1.2.0 parallel_4.0.3    expm_0.999-5

```

```

[66] rematch2_2.1.2      RColorBrewer_1.1-2    yaml_2.2.1            curl_4.3              memoise_1.1.0
[71] gdttools_0.2.2       stringi_1.5.3         RSQLite_2.2.1        desc_1.2.0           leafpop_0.0.6
[76] e1071_1.7-4         crancache_0.0.0.9001  boot_1.3-25          pkgbuild_1.1.0       repr_1.1.0
[81] systemfonts_0.3.2   rlang_0.4.8           pkgconfig_2.0.3      prompt_1.0.0         evaluate_0.14
[86] lattice_0.20-41     tensor_1.5            purrr_0.3.4          htmlwidgets_1.5.2    bit_4.0.4
[91] processx_3.4.4     tidysselect_1.1.0    magrittr_2.0.1       R6_2.5.0             generics_0.1.0
[96] DBI_1.1.0           mgcv_1.8-33          pillar_1.4.7         withr_2.3.0          tibble_3.0.4
[101] crayon_1.3.4        uuid_0.1-4           KernSmooth_2.23-18   rmarkdown_2.5        usethis_1.6.3
[106] grid_4.0.3          blob_1.2.1           callr_3.5.1          git2r_0.27.1         webshot_0.5.2
[111] digest_0.6.27      classInt_0.4-3       brew_1.0-6           stats4_4.0.3         munsell_0.5.0
[116] viridisLite_0.3.0  skimmr_2.1.2         sessioninfo_1.1.1

> sf_extSoftVersion()
      GEOS          GDAL      proj.4 GDAL_with_GEOS  USE_PROJ_H
"3.8.1"    "3.1.3"    "7.1.1"    "true"      "true"

> sink(type = "message")

> sink()

```

Citing this document

Daniel Nüst (2020). CODECHECK Certificate 2020-025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279275>

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About this document

This document was created using [R Markdown](#) using the `codecheck` R package. `make codecheck.pdf` will regenerate the report file.

`sessionInfo()`

```
## R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)
## Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
## Running under: Ubuntu 20.04 LTS
##
## Matrix products: default
## BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/libblas.so.3
## LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/liblapack.so.3
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8      LC_NUMERIC=C
## [3] LC_TIME=de_DE.UTF-8      LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8
## [5] LC_MONETARY=de_DE.UTF-8  LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8
## [7] LC_PAPER=de_DE.UTF-8    LC_NAME=C
## [9] LC_ADDRESS=C             LC_TELEPHONE=C
## [11] LC_MEASUREMENT=de_DE.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets
## [6] methods   base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] readr_1.4.0      tibble_3.0.4
## [3] xtable_1.8-4    yaml_2.2.1
## [5] rprojroot_2.0.2  knitr_1.30
## [7] codecheck_0.0.0.9010 parsedate_1.2.0
## [9] R.cache_0.14.0   gh_1.2.0
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] git2r_0.27.1     compiler_4.0.3   pillar_1.4.7
## [4] base64enc_0.1-3 R.methodsS3_1.8.1 R.utils_2.10.1
## [7] tools_4.0.3     rorcid_0.6.4     digest_0.6.27
## [10] jsonlite_1.7.2  evaluate_0.14    memoise_1.1.0
## [13] lifecycle_0.2.0 pkgconfig_2.0.3  rlang_0.4.9
## [16] cli_2.2.0       crul_1.0.0       curl_4.3
## [19] xfun_0.19       withr_2.3.0      repr_1.1.0
## [22] dplyr_1.0.2     httr_1.4.2       stringr_1.4.0
```

```
## [25] hms_0.5.3          fauxpas_0.5.0      generics_0.1.0
## [28] fs_1.5.0           vctrs_0.3.5       tidyselect_1.1.0
## [31] glue_1.4.2        httpcode_0.3.0    R6_2.5.0
## [34] fansi_0.4.1       rmarkdown_2.6     tidyr_1.1.2
## [37] skimr_2.1.2       whisker_0.4       purrr_0.3.4
## [40] magrittr_2.0.1    osfr_0.2.8        htmltools_0.5.0
## [43] ellipsis_0.3.1    assertthat_0.2.1 utf8_1.1.4
## [46] stringi_1.5.3     crayon_1.3.4      R.oo_1.24.0
```